

The underlying signals of efficiency in European universities: a combined efficiency and machine learning approach

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Summary

1. We explore the underlying mechanisms that drive efficiency in European universities and identify the most relevant variables in predicting the efficiency level.
2. We rely on a panel dataset covering 235 European universities over 2011-2019 for a wide set of variables.
3. Universities can increase their outputs by 20% while maintaining the same level of inputs.
4. Policy initiatives to promote international student mobility, enable broader student participation to Erasmus and exchange programs without financial barriers, are required.
5. Policy makers should enhance the Ph.D. programs, by both increasing the opportunities to go abroad for Ph.D. students and enhancing the job market access for Ph.D. graduates.

1. Introduction

The reliance of higher education institutions (HEIs) on government funding subjects them to the constraints of state budgets (Agasisti & Johnes, 2015). This financial limitation poses a significant challenge for HEIs as they strive to maintain competitiveness in an increasingly demanding environment. Consequently, evaluating the efficiency of HEIs and identifying the key factors behind efficiency levels provides insights into the practices of

the most successful institutions and guides future strategic decisions.

The present policy brief aims to explore the underlying mechanisms that drive efficiency, exploring what matters the most in predicting the efficiency level of European universities.

2. Data and Methodology

The study of Dipierro and De Witte (2024) aims to understand how internal characteristics of universities contribute to their efficiency. It relies on data from the European Tertiary Education Register (ETER), which provides an interesting dataset to evaluate European universities over a variety of dimensions, and over a long-time horizon. In particular, it focusses on 235 universities that provide ISCED 5-8 levels, including short-cycle tertiary education, bachelor's, master's and doctoral, or equivalent levels. The sampled universities are from Austria (16), Cyprus (2), Germany (67), Ireland (6), Liechtenstein (1), Malta (1), the Netherlands (13), Sweden (23), Switzerland (10) and the UK (92). Data span from 2011 to 2019.

The first stage of the analysis benchmarks the universities with respect to their ability of turning inputs (including primary human and financial resources) into outputs (teaching and research outcomes). We employ a nonparametric efficiency technique that is particularly suitable for evaluating the complex operations of universities: Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA).

In the second stage of our study, we investigate the factors that influence the efficiency of the universities in our sample. Specifically, we assess 33 variables to determine their importance in predicting efficiency. To achieve this, we employ a Feature Selection technique from the field of Machine Learning.

3. Results

Our findings reveal significant potential for improving efficiency, aligning with recent

studies (Daraio et al., 2021; Herberholz and Wigger, 2021). Although there was a slight decline in efficiency between 2015 and 2017, the later years of the study show a significant acceleration in efficiency gains. The average efficiency score for the entire period is 0.80, indicating that universities could, on average, increase their outputs by about 20% with the given level of inputs. Figure 1 provides detailed information on the average values and the first and third quartiles of efficiency scores throughout the period.

Country-level analysis reveals upward efficiency trends across all sampled countries, with the only exception of Lithuania, which showed a slight decrease of 1%. Cyprus, Austria, and Sweden produced the most significant efficiency improvements comparing 2011 and 2019 values.

Additionally, our findings reveal that certain characteristics are pivotal in determining universities' effective functioning and quality management, thereby serving as key drivers for higher efficiency values. Specifically, Figure 2 visualizes the variables that influence most the efficiency scores. It reveals that the Ph.D. intensity, the specialization index of graduates at level 8, the number of ISCED 8 graduates, the number of Erasmus outgoing and incoming students, the proportion of women among ISCED 5-7 students, and the legal status (particularly in public universities) show notable associations with higher efficiency.

Interestingly, amongst the most important variables that predict efficiency, the amount of tuition fees stands out. In this sense, higher tuition fees can attract top talents to universities, enabling them to select the best students and researchers in a sort of self-selection setting (Ferro and D'Elia, 2020). This selection process potentially enhances

the institutions' overall efficiency and effectiveness (Daraio et al., 2015). However, despite the strong positive correlation, also the opposite emerges for some institutions. This might be due to resource misallocation, reduced access from low-income students, or financial burdens on students that result in higher dropout or more student jobs (and consequently lower performance). These findings support the arguments of Bolli et al. (2016), Daraio et al. (2015), Horta and Lacy (2011). Importantly, the relationships identified are more indicative of correlations rather than causations.

4. Policy recommendations

The insights offer a guidance for understanding the complex dynamics influencing universities' efficiency and can inform strategic decisions in the sector.

The results suggest that policymakers should focus on enhancing Ph.D. programs by supporting the creation of strong research units, fostering more extensive international networks, and increasing opportunities for Ph.D. students to study abroad. This requires action to increase Ph.D. research funding and adjust it according to the cost of living in different countries. Additionally, policies should improve job market access for Ph.D. graduates. By doing so, it is possible to encourage more talented students and researchers to pursue advanced studies, ultimately benefiting university efficiency and academic excellence.

Additionally, the results highlight the importance of promoting international student mobility and encouraging more active participation in Erasmus+ and exchange programs. Currently, students' socio-economic backgrounds significantly influence their decision to join these programs. To

address this, it is necessary to increase the funding available to students studying or working abroad during their university years. Increased funding for these initiatives is crucial to enable broader student participation without financial barriers.

Finally, university administrators should be strongly encouraged to closely monitor and evaluate internal processes to prevent efficiency losses. This involves implementing robust data collection and analysis systems to regularly assess performance metrics, identify inefficiencies, and address them promptly. Administrators should also foster a culture of continuous improvement, where feedback from faculty, staff, and students is actively sought and used to refine administrative and operational practices. Additionally, investing in training and development programs for administrative personnel can enhance their skills in managing resources efficiently.

Based on these findings, policymakers should design and implement policies aimed at increasing university efficiency and reducing disparities across Europe. These findings underscore the need for European policies that provide robust support to key factors influencing university performance. Such policies should focus on enhancing research funding, promoting international collaboration, and supporting student mobility programs. These efforts will not only enhance the performance of individual institutions but also contribute to a more equitable and effective higher education system across Europe.

What is EFFEct?

EFFEct is an impact-driven research project aiming to enhance the quality of education in the EU by providing evidence-based policy recommendations and conducting rigorous research on the education policies of individual EU member states.

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Figures

Figure 1: Efficiency score of the sampled 235 European universities over the 2011-2019 period.

Note: Q1 and Q3 refer respectively to the first and third quartiles of the efficiency distribution.

Figure 2: SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) of the most important features on efficiency score. Positive SHAP values on x-axis indicate that the respective y-axis feature values lead to the efficiency increase, and vice versa.

Note: The displayed features are: *Stud Fees Funds* (tuition fees), *Ph.D. Intens* (share of graduates at ISCED 8 by graduates at ISCED 5-7), *HI Grad 8* (Herfindahl index of Ph.D. graduates by field of education), *Grad 8* (Ph.D. graduates), *Foreign Grad 8* (share of foreigners Ph.D. graduates), *Eras Out Stud* (outgoing Erasmus students), *Foreign Stud 5-7* (share of foreigners students at ISCED 5-7), *Foreign Grad 5-7* (share of foreigners students at ISCED 5-7), *Stud 8* (Ph.D. students), *Wom Stud 5-7* (share of women students at ISCED 5-7), *Erasm In Stud* (ingoing Erasmus students), *Status* (public or otherwise), *Dem event* (subject to a demographic event - e.g. birth, closure, merger - or otherwise).

Further Information:

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